

TYPES OF WORK AND DESIGN STAGES IN RAILWAY CONSTRUCTION

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Annotation: This article examines the types of work, periods and design stages in railway construction. The essence of feasibility studies has been studied.

Keywords: period, finishing, project, working document, structure, solid, sleeper, electric, water.

Entrance part: Today, the role of rail transport is of great importance in the economy of our mamalakat. Therefore, the study of innovations and shortcomings in this area is an urgent task.

Railway Construction-very murrakkab is a multi-gravel procedure, it covers all construction and construction installation works within its scope.

The process of general construction work is carried out within three periods: preparatory, basic and finishing (finishing) and auxiliary work is carried out.

During the preparatory period, the necessary work is carried out to expand the construction of the main objects, railway structural elements, that is, the preparatory work of the territory (deforestation, extraction of pigs, cleaning of the separated corridor, demolition and relocation of buildings, etc.).k.), which includes the construction of temporary buildings and structures, the construction of temporary highways and the construction of communication lines. Preparatory period work is 5-8% of the total construction work cost.

The work of the main period begins with the construction of artificial structures (water pipes, small bridges). The cost of the construction of artificial

structures is 4-16% of the total work complex, depending on the region of construction execution.

the construction of the Earth chamber is made up of lifting, carving, water-escaping and regulatory devices. earthwork is considered a profitable and expensive work, and total construction work is 15-30% of the cost.

Next, the upper device of the track is laid: after laying the relso-traverse bars, the ballast layers 1st layer (sand) and 2nd layer (shepen) materials are laid on it. The cost of the upper device of the road is 15-30% of the cost of general construction work.

Also, electricity, water, gas supply and sewerage facilities will be built, the cost of which is up to 10% of the total construction cost.

In order to transfer the railway to permanent use, automatics, telemechanics and communication lines, traffic lights, communication houses must be built, the cost of which is 1.5-3.6% of the total construction work cost.

During the closing period, preparatory work is carried out for the permanent commissioning of the railway: the road consists of post-sinking repairs, construction of road crossing sites (pereyezds), installation of shlagbaums, installation of stiffeners (protivougones).

Types of railway construction include:

- * construction of new railway lines;
- * construction of second roads;
- * railway electrification;
- reconstruction of the station and uzels.

The solution for the organization of railway construction is accepted at the time of the development of the project and the implementation of the construction. When drawing up a project of a railway construction organization, the implementation of the construction on etap in the construction organization Project, characteristics of the complexity and conditions of construction, is carried out, determining the necessary resources for each etap.

Before the development of the project of the organization of railway construction is carried out works “feasibility study” (TIA).

"Feasibility study" and "feasibility study" are necessary to determine the parameters and directions of the railway to be designed.

The design of railway construction is mainly carried out in two stages “project” and “working document”. Great importance in the construction of the “project” is given to the solutions for the organization of construction.

” Basic project solutions “(ALE) of the” project”, a principled scheme of the construction organization is developed and compared.

For the construction of each next Railway, a “project” is developed, one of the main parts of which is the “project for the organization of construction” (QTL), which is the basis for drawing up a construction estimate, is used in the distribution of capital funds and in future production planning.

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